

ISSN: 3060-4613

MAKTABGACHA
VA MAKTAB
TA'LIMI VAZIRLIGI

O'zbekiston
Milliy Pedagogika
Universiteti

№2(1)
2026

- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

M

AKTABGACHA VA AKTAB TA'LIMI

Pedagogika, psixologiya fanlariga ixtisoslashgan ilmiy jurnal

MAKTABGACHA VA MAKTAB TA'LIMI

Elektron nashr. 638 sahifa,
2-fevral, 2026-yil.

BOSH MUHARRIR:

Karimova E'zoza Gapijanovna – O'zbekiston Respublikasi Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi vaziri

BOSH MUHARRIR O'RINBOSARI:

Ibragimova Gulsanam Ne'matovna – Pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor

TAHRIRIYAT KENGASHI A'ZOLARI

Ibragimov X.I. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, akademik
Shoumarov G'.B. – psixologiya fanlari doktori, akademik
Qirg'izboyev A.K. – Tarix fanlari doktori, professor
Jamoldinova O.R. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Sharipov Sh.S. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Shermuhhammadov B.Sh. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Ma'murov B.B. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Madraximova F.R. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Kalonov M.B. – iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor
Nabiyev D.X. – iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor
Qo'ldoshev Q. M. – iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor
Ikramxanova F.I. – filologiya fanlari doktori, professor
Ismagilova F.S. – psixologiya fanlari doktori, professor (Rossiya)
Stoyuxina N.Yu. – psixologiya fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (Rossiya)
Magauova A.S. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor (Qozog'iston)
Rejep O'zyurek – psixologiya fanlari doktori, professor (Turkiya)
Wookyuu Cha – Koreya milliy ta'lim universiteti rektori (Koreya)
Polonnikov A.A. – psixologiya fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (Belarus)
Mizayeva F. O. – Pedagogika fanlari doktori, dotsent
Baybayeva M.X. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Muxsiyeva A.T. – pedagogika fanlari doktori, professor
Aliyev B. – falsafa fanlari doktori, professor
Abdullayeva N. Sh. – Pedagogika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
G'afurov D. O. – falsafa fanlari doktori (Phd)
Shomurodov R.T. – iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi (PhD), dotsent
Mirzayeva F. O. – pedagogika fanlari doktori (DSc), dotsent
Jalilova S.X. – psixologiya fanlari nomzodi (PhD), dotsent
Bafayev M.M. – psixologiya fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Usmonova D.I. – Samarqand iqtisodiyot va servis institute dotsenti
Saifnazarov I. – falsafa fanlari doktori, professor
Nematov Sh.E. – pedagogika fanlari nomzodi (PhD)
Tillashayxova X.A. – psixologiya fanlari nomzodi (PhD), dotsent
Yuldasheva F.I. – pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Doniyorov S. M. – "Yangi O'zbekiston" va "Pravda Vostoka" gazetalarini tahririyati DM bosh muharriri, O'zbekiston Respublikasida xizmat ko'rsatgan jurnalist, filologiya fanlari nomzodi (PhD)
Yuldasheva D.B. – filologiya fanlari bo'yicha falsafa (PhD) doktori, dotsent
Tangriyev A. T. – Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti kafedra professori
Ashurov R. R. – psixologiya fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Panjiyev M. A. – Qashqadaryo viloyati Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi boshqarmasi boshlig'ining birinchi o'rinbosari
Xudayberganov N. A. – Xorazm Ma'mun akademiyasi Tabiiy fanlar bo'limining katta ilmiy xodimi, biologiya fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Vaxobov Anvar Abdusattor o'g'li – Pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori, dotsent

Muassis: "Tadbirkor va ishbilarmon" MChJ

Hamkorlarimiz: O'zbekiston Respublikasi Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi vazirligi, O'zbekiston milliy pedagogika universiteti

EDITOR-IN-CHIEF:

Karimova E'zoza Gapirzhanovna – Minister of Perschool and School Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan

DEPUTY EDITOR-IN-CHIEF:

Ibragimova Gulsanam Ne'matovna – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

EDITORIAL BOARD MEMBERS:

Ibragimov X.I. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Academician

Shoumarov G. B. – Doctor of Psychological Sciences, Academician

Qirg'izboyev A. K. – Doctor of Historical Sciences, Professor

Jamoldinova O.R. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Sharipov Sh.S. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Shermuhhammadov B.Sh. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Ma'murov B.B. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Madraximova F.R. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Kalonov M.B. – Doctor of Economic Sciences, Professor

Nabiyev D.X. – Doctor of Economic Sciences, Professor

Koldoshev K. M. – Doctor of Economic Sciences, Professor

Ikramxanova F.I. – Doctor of Philological Sciences, Professor

Ismagilova F.S. – Doctor of Psychological Sciences, Professor (Russia)

Stoyuxina N.Yu. – Candidate of Psychological Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor (Russia)

Magauova A.S. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor (Kazakhstan)

Rejep O'zyurek – Doctor of Psychological Sciences, Professor (Turkey)

Wookyu Cha – President of the National University of Education, Korea (South Korea)

Polonnikov A.A. – Candidate of Psychological Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor (Belarus)

Mizayeva F. O. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Baybayeva M.X. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Muxsiyeva A.T. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, Professor

Aliyev B. – Doctor of philosophy, professor

Abdullayeva N. Sh. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences (DSc), Professor

Gafurov D. O. – Doctor of Philosophy (PhD)

Shomurodov R.T. – Candidate of Economic Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor

Mirzayeva F. O. – Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences (DSc), Associate Professor

Jalilova S.X. – Candidate of Psychological Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor

Bafayev M.M. – Doctor of Philosophy in Psychological Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor

Usmonova D.I. – Associate Professor, Samarkand Institute of Economics and Service

Saifnazarov I. – Doctor of philosophy, professor

Nematov Sh.E. – Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences (PhD)

Tillashayxova X.A. – Candidate of Psychological Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor

Yuldasheva F.I. – Doctor of Philosophy in Pedagogical Sciences (PhD), Associate Professor

Doniyorov S. M. – Editor-in-Chief of the Editorial Board of the newspapers "Yangi Uzbekiston" and "Pravda Vostoka", Honored Journalist of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Candidate of Philological Sciences (PhD)

Yuldasheva D.B. – Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Philological Sciences, Associate Professor

Tangriyev A.T. – is a professor of Tashkent State University of Economics

Ashurov R. R. – Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Psychology, Associate Professor

Panjiyev M. A. – First Deputy Head of the Department of Preschool and School Education of the Kashkadarya Region

Khudaiberganov N. A. – Senior Researcher of the Department of Natural Sciences of the Khorezm Mamun

Academy, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Biological Sciences

Vakhobov Anvar Abdusattor oglu – Doctor of Philosophy in Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor

“Maktabgacha va maktab ta’limi” jurnali O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy attestatsiya komissiyasining quyidagi qarorlariga asosan pedagogika va psixologiya fanlari bo‘yicha falsafa doktori (PhD) hamda fan doktori (DSc) ilmiy darajasiga talabgorlarning dissertatsiyalaridagi asosiy ilmiy natijalarni chop etish uchun milliy ilmiy nashrlar ro‘yxatiga kiritilgan:

Pedagogika fanlari bo‘yicha: OAK Kengashi tavsiyasi (26.08.2024-y., №11-05-4381/01) asosida:

- Ekspert kengashi (29.10.2024-y., №10)
- Rayosat qarori (31.10.2024-y., №363/5)

Psixologiya fanlari bo‘yicha: Toshkent davlat pedagogika universiteti murojaatiga asosan OAK tavsiyasi (24.04.2025-y., №11-05-2566/01):

- Ekspert kengashi (25.05.2025-y., №10)
- Rayosat qarori (08.05.2025-y., №370/5)

“Maktabgacha va maktab ta’limi”
jurnali

26.09.2023-yildan

O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti
Administratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot
va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar
agentligi tomonidan **№C-5669363**
reyestr raqami tartibi bo‘yicha
ro‘yxatdan o‘tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: **№136361**

MUNDARIJA

O'quvchilarni intellektual rivojlantirishning psixologik omillari.....	22
<i>Ashurov Ramzidin Ramazonovich</i>	
Maktabgacha ta'limda bolaning kitobxonlik madaniyatini shakllantirishda oila bilan ishlashning nazariy asoslari	27
<i>Jumanova Fatima Uralovna, Allaberganova Munisa Begimboy qizi</i>	
Maktabgacha ta'lim tizimida axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalaridan samarali foydalanishning metodologik asoslari	32
<i>Jo'rayeva Nargiza Tairovna, Bekbergenova Yulduz Tanirbergen qizi</i>	
Faoliyatli yondashuv asosida maktabgacha 6-7 yoshli bolalarda nutqiy ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish metodikasi	35
<i>Ziyodullayeva Mohirabonu Ikromjon qizi</i>	
Davlat ta'lim muassasalarida manfaatlar to'qnashuvini boshqarishning tashkiliy-huquqiy mexanizmlari ...	39
<i>Xaybatullaeva Sojidxon Ziyatullayevna</i>	
Umumta'lim maktablarida jismoniy tarbiya darslarining samaradorligini oshirishda integratsion yondashuv	42
<i>Kamoliddinov Mirzohid</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining mantiqiy tafakkurini rivojlantirishda interfaol metodlarning samaradorligi	45
<i>Kamoliddinova Dilnoza Axmadilaxanovna</i>	
Bo'lajak tarbiyachilarda kreativ faollikni rivojlantirish mexanizmlari.....	48
<i>Nurjanova Rayxan Urazbaevna</i>	
Sinf biologiya fanini o'qitishda TIMSS topshiriqlardan foydalanish metodikasi va baholash mezonlari	52
<i>Xaitboyeva Dilorom Rustam qizi</i>	
Qandli diabet tashxisli bemorlarda shaxs tuzilmasining emotsional komponentlari	56
<i>Sadikova Umida Botirovna</i>	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalar nutqini rivojlantirishda pedagogik diagnostikani amalga oshirishning natijaviyligi	60
<i>Maxmutazimova Yulduz Raxmatovna, Qodirova Shaxnoza Saidazim qizi</i>	
Kasbiy imij shakllanishida psixologik jihatlarning tafovutlari	64
<i>Aminova Dilnoza Orifjonovna</i>	
Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlari direktorlarining jamoa bilan ishlash jarayonida yetakchilik kompetensiyalarini rivojlantirish	69
<i>Abdiyeva Fazilat Fayzulla qizi</i>	
Kichik maktab yoshidagi bolalar shaxsi rivojlanishida psixologik moslashuvning tipik xususiyatlari	73
<i>Mirsaitova Guzal Baxodirovna</i>	
Oliy ta'lim tizimida variativ modellashtirish asosida talabalarning kreativ faoliyatini rivojlantirishda zamonaviy pedagogik texnologiyalarining qo'llanilishi	76
<i>Quvvatova Mohira Hikmatillayevna</i>	
Interfaol treninglar orqali o'qituvchilarning innovatsion fikrlashini rivojlantirish tajribasi	79
<i>Abdiyeva Shodiyona Yodgor qizi</i>	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda milliy qadriyatlar asosida axloqiy tarbiyani shakllantirishning ahamiyati.....	82
<i>Zulayxo Nazarova, Qarshiboyeva Muxlisa Ismatullo qizi</i>	
Ijodiy qobiliyatni o'stirishda pedagogik mahorat va innovatsion metodlar	85
<i>Mutallibova Odinaxon Mirzaolimjon qizi</i>	
Umumiy o'rta ta'lim maktablarida olimpiadalarga tayyorlashda masalalar yechish texnologiyasi 11-sinf misolida	89
<i>Aslonov Xayrullo Shukrullo o'g'li</i>	

Bokschi qizlarni texnika taktikasini takomillashtirish.....	94
<i>Axmedov Latifjon G'ayrat o'g'li</i>	
Ixtisoslashtirilgan terminologiyaning asosiy lingvistik xususiyatlari	99
<i>Axmedova Dilnoza Anvarovna</i>	
Interfaol metodlar orqali zamonaviy darslarni tashkil etishning o'ziga xos tendensiyalari.....	102
<i>Bakirov Otabek Bo'ranovich</i>	
Boshqaruv psixologiyasi terminlarini tarjima qilishning metodologik muammolari	106
<i>D. J. Norboyeva</i>	
Raqamli transformatsiya sharoitida oliy ta'lim muassasalari talabalari ruhiyatiga virtual muhitning salbiy ta'siri.....	110
<i>Giyosov Ulug'bek Eshpulatovich, Turayeva Nigora Husniddin qizi</i>	
Hamshiralik ishida raqamli texnologiyalardan foydalanishning samaradorligi.....	113
<i>Rasulova Gulmira, Amonova Dildora, Abdurahmonov Aziz, Hakimova X. X.</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida kognitiv qobiliyatlarni shakllantirishda zamonaviy pedagogik yondashuvlar	117
<i>Jumayev Xushboq Soatmumin o'g'li</i>	
Principles of Organising Autonomous Learning.....	121
<i>Khazratova Zukhra Mamaraimovna</i>	
Najot – ta'limda, najot-tarbiyada	124
<i>Mo'minova Manzura Mamasodiqjonovna</i>	
Educational Potential of Museum Pedagogy and Criteria for its Application in Developing Historical Thinking of Pre-Service History Teachers.....	127
<i>Niyozov Javlonbek</i>	
Landshaft dizayni vastasida bo'lajak maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlari tarbiyachilarining estetik va kreativ ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish	131
<i>Radjapova Zuxra Tirkashevna</i>	
Abdulla Avloniy pedagogik merosida shaxs psixologiyasi masalalari.....	134
<i>S. O. Mamarasulov, D. A. Egamberdiyeva</i>	
TBL metodini qo'llash orqali o'quvchilarning madaniyati va ijtimoiy muloqot ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish....	138
<i>Sodikova Oyshakhon Muxammadsodik</i>	
Pedagogik innovatsiyalarni boshqarishning nazariy-metodologik asoslari.....	142
<i>Solihova Barno Sodiq qizi</i>	
Boshlang'ich ta'lim magistratura talabalarining ijodiy faolligini rivojlantirish shart-sharoitlari	146
<i>Yarmatov Shermo'min Rahmatovich</i>	
Формирование готовности родителей детей старшего дошкольного возраста к выполнению воспитательной функции в семье.....	149
<i>Атаджанова Сохиба Талиповна</i>	
Redjio pedagogik yondashuv asosida maktabgacha katta yoshdagi bolalarda mantiqiy fikrlash ko'nikmalarini shakllantirish pedagogik muammo sifatida	152
<i>Djamilova Nargiza Nuritdinovna, Otahonova Marjona</i>	
Talabalarda algoritmik kompetentlikni rivojlantirishning sun'iy intellekt va Big Data Analytics asosida o'quv faoliyatini real vaqt rejimida kuzatuvchi va boshqaruvchi konseptual modelni takomillashtirish.....	155
<i>Kayumova Nazokat Rashitovna</i>	
Raqamli ta'lim muhitida chet tili o'qituvchilari va talabalar o'rtasidagi interaktsiyaning pedagogik samaradorligi va innovatsion mexanizmlari	163
<i>Eshonqulova Umida Xolmirzayevna</i>	
MTTlarda nutqni rivojlantirishga doir mashg'ulotlarda interfaol usullardan foydalanish texnologiyasi	168
<i>To'laboyeva Iqbolaxon Olimjonovna</i>	
Ta'lim jarayonidagi konfliktlar.....	173
<i>Abulova Mohigul Komiljonzoda</i>	
Talabalarining bolalarda ijtimoiy moslashuvni shakllantirishga kasbiy tayyorgarligini takomillashtirish	176
<i>Inomova Mahliyo Yusuf qizi</i>	

MUNDARIJA	СОДЕРЖАНИЕ	CONTENTS
		Shaxs tuzilmasida ma'naviy intellekt: nazariy-metodologik tahlil va psixologik interpretatsiya 179 Mirxoliqova Charos Xabibullaevna
		18-20 yoshli belbog'li kurashchilarning musobaqa oldi jismoniy tayyorgarliklari 183 Muzafarov Muxammadali Maxsudovich
		Talabalarda mustaqil ta'lim topshiriqlaridan foydalanib kasbiy madaniyatini rivojlantirishga zamonaviy yondashuvlar (boshlang'ich ta'limda tarbiya fani misolida) 187 Yadgarova Surayyo
		Maktab o'quvchilariga pedagogik ta'sir ko'rsatishda o'quvchilarning individual xususiyatlarini hisobga olish 190 Yo'ldoshova Shahlo Shukurullo qizi
		Bo'lajak boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilarini ma'naviy-ma'rifiy faoliyatga tayyorgarligini rivojlantirishning nazariy tahlili 194 Yusupova Sanobar Odil qizi
		Типология научного текста: от жанровой классификации к дискурсивной модели 197 Бахтияр Катибжанович Саттаров
		Взаимодействие педагога и семьи в профилактике и преодолении стресса у детей дошкольного возраста 201 Г. С. Алиходжаева, Х. Рахимова
		Условия эффективности инклюзивного образования 206 Г. С. Алиходжаева, Л. О. Бекмуродова
		Педагогическая готовность к обучению в школе детей билингов 211 Г. С. Алиходжаева, Н. А. Ганиева
		Педагогические условия формирования эмоционального интеллекта у дошкольников 216 Джалилова Феруза Намазовна
		Milliy meros va musiqiy madaniyatning yosh avlod tarbiyasidagi o'rni 219 Zuhriddin Azizov
		Госпитальная школа как пространство поддержки и развития ребёнка (на примере госпитальной школы при детской клиники Синсиннати, США) 222 Муминов Р. Р., Хакимова Н. Х., Набиева Г. Г.
		Интерактивные формы работы в процессе профориентации детей дошкольного возраста 227 Н. Т. Жураева, С. М. Ахмеджанова
		Samarali hamkorlikdagi faoliyatga tayyorlashga oid yondashuvlar 231 Hojiyeva Zulfiya O'ktamovna
		Поэтапное вовлечение детей с расстройствами аутистического спектра в дошкольное инклюзивное образование: комплексный анализ научно-теоретических и практических подходов 234 Сабина Рагимова Ровшан кызы, Айсель Масимова Арастун кызы
		Umumta'lim maktablarida fizika fanini o'qitish metodikasini rivojlantirishda sun'iy intellektdan foydalanishni boshqarishni takomillashtirish 245 Allaniyazova Bibigul Sarsenbay qizi
		Boshlang'ich sinflarda ona tili va o'qish savodxonligi darslariga kreativ fikrlash asosida tayyorlash 248 Botirova Jumagul Chori qizi
		Boshlang'ich sinflarda fanlarni o'qitish metodikasini rivojlantirishda sun'iy intellektdan foydalanishni boshqarishni takomillashtirish 254 Kaypova Gulnara Muratbaevna
		Umumta'lim maktablarida tabiiy-ilmiy savodxonlik ko'nikmalarining rivojlantirish masalalari 257 Davletova Hamida Xasan qizi
		Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarini ma'naviy axloqiy ruhda tarbiyalashning psixologik jihatlari 261 Fayzullayev Ermat Majidovich, Ortiqova Mashxura
		Orkestr va ansambllarning fan sifatidagi o'rni va tarbiyaviy ahamiyati 265 Fayzullayev Ermat Majidovich
		Maktab fizika darslarida interaktiv dasturlar va simulyatorlardan foydalanish metodikasi 269 Xayriddinova Malikaxon Qodirxon qizi

Musiqada midi musiqiy cholg'ularning raqamli interfeysi.....	274
<i>Omonov Xasanxon Sulaymonovich</i>	
Karyera o'sishida gender tafovutlarning ahamiyati.....	277
<i>Yulchiboyeva Nazokatxon Iqboljon qizi</i>	
Bo'lajak musiqa o'qituvchilarining kreativlik sifatlarini rivojlantirishga ta'sir etuvchi pedagogik omillar	283
<i>Omonov Xasanxon Sulaymonovich, Normuradova Nafisa Kuchkarovna</i>	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarning ekologik tarbiyasi – ijtimoiy pedagogik muammo sifatida	287
<i>Kasimova Dilrabo Baxadirovna, Marjona Atoyeva Ismat qizi</i>	
Ilk yoshdagi bolalar psixologiyasi va rivojlanish xususiyatlari.....	291
<i>Kayumova Nargiza Mirziyatovna, Ne'matjonova Gulzira Ne'matjon qizi</i>	
Jadid pedagogik tafakkurida "o'qituvchi" fenomeni.....	294
<i>Xushbokov Oybek Uralovich</i>	
Maktabga tayyorlov guruhi tarbiyalanuvchilarida savol berish malakalarini shakllantirish	296
<i>Erhanova Nasiba Absayitovna</i>	
Musiqiy ta'limda xalq va zamonaviy qo'shiqlar vositasida maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarning etnomadaniy komponentlarni shakllantirish	298
<i>Qurbanova Muslima Shavkatbek qizi</i>	
Umumta'lim maktablari o'quvchilarida tadbirkorlik ko'nikmalarini tarkib toptirish metodikasi (biologiya fani misolida).....	300
<i>Akmalova Farida Dilmurod qizi</i>	
Maktabgacha ta'limda adaptiv ta'lim texnologiyalari yordamida bolalar ijodkorlik ko'nikmasini shakllantirish mazmuni.....	304
<i>To'xliboyeva Zuxra Abdumutal qizi</i>	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi iqtidorli bolalar bilan ishlashda ta'lim texnologiyasi	308
<i>Xudoyberdiyeva Durdona Baxodir qizi</i>	
Pedagogik-psixologik qarashlarda otaning oiladagi o'rni haqidagi tasavvurlarni shakllantirish dinamikasiga oid fikrlar talqini.....	311
<i>Karshiyeva Dilafuz Suyunovna, Maxamatova Munisa Mamirzo qizi</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilariga ingliz tilini o'qitishning nazariy va amaliy asoslari	314
<i>Axmatqulova Maxfuza Shuhrat qizi</i>	
Integrativ yondashuv asosida bo'lajak o'qituvchilarda interpersonal intellekt ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish ...	318
<i>G'ulomova Oychehra No'monjon qizi</i>	
Etnomadaniy qadriyatlarni integratsiyalashgan ta'lim jarayonida maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarga singdirishning samarali yo'llari	321
<i>G'ulomxo'jayeva Mushtariy Elmurod qizi</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinf ona tili darslarida grafik organayzerlardan foydalanish	324
<i>Iroda Isroilova</i>	
Buxoro iqlimi va tabiiy resurslaridan samarali foydalanish: ekologik va fizik-geografik yondashuv	329
<i>Mardonova Saodat Muzaffarovna</i>	
Effective Traditional and Innovative Approaches in English Language Teaching: Evidence From EFL Classrooms	333
<i>Yuldoshev Khaydarbek</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining lug'at boyligini rivojlantirishda lingvopedagogik yondashuvning nazariy-metodologik asoslari.....	336
<i>Allayarova Sojida Umirzakovna</i>	
Механизмы использования цифровых педагогических технологий для обеспечения непрерывности образовательного процесса учащихся начальных классов в условиях длительного лечения	339
<i>Турсунова Д. З., Холлиева Н. Х.</i>	
Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlarida o'tkazilgan o'yin faoliyatlarini bolalar ovozi talaffuzining takomillashuviga ta'siri	342
<i>Kattaxo'jayeva Shaxlohon Bohodirovna</i>	

MUNDARIJA СОДЕРЖАНИЕ CONTENTS	O'qituvchilar tayyorlashda pedagogik innovatsiyalar va milliy kontentni integratsiya qilish strategiyalari ... 344 Rahmatova Feruza Qudrat qizi	344
Maktabgacha katta yoshdagi bolalarni maktab ta'limiga tayyorlash jarayonini tashkil etishda tizimli yondashuv 348 Abdusamatova Nargiza Jamoliddinovna	348	
Moliyaviy savodxonlik asoslarini shakllantirish uchun "Tejamkor bola" o'yinli ta'lim faoliyatini asosida ishlashni takomillashtirilish..... 352 Rizayeva Munisxon Maxkamovna	352	
Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlarida byudjet hisobi standartlariga (BHS) muvofiq buxgalteriya hisobini tashkil qilish va yuritish tartib-qoidalari..... 356 Boltayev Ahmad Rustamjonovich	356	
Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlari moliyaviy munosabatlarning huquqiy asoslari 359 Boymuradov Normurod Abdusadikovich	359	
Oliy ta'lim muassasalarida jismoniy tarbiya va sportni rivojlantirishning metodologik asoslari..... 362 Ma'rufov Mansurbek Musajonovich, Xonimov Mirqosim Samatqul o'g'li	362	
O'smirlarda liderlik xususiyatlarini rivojlantirishning ijtimoiy-psixologik xususiyatlari..... 367 Salayeva Dilafuz Buranovna	367	
Pedagog nutq madaniyatining milliy va umuminsoniy qadriyatlarga ta'siri..... 370 Toshtemirova Nigina Normurod qizi	370	
Новые методы обучения устному переводу студентов-переводчиков..... 373 Уринбаева Дилдора Утепбергеновна	373	
O'quvchilarda axborot iste'moli madaniyatini rivojlantirishning pedagogik tuzilmasi 376 Muxammadiyev Baxtiyor Jurayevich	376	
Boshlang'ich ta'limda o'quvchilarning o'qish savodxonligini xalqaro mezonlar asosida rivojlantirish yo'llari 380 Axrorov Voris Yunusovich, Botirova Ozoda Nasir qizi	380	
Ta'lim sifatini baholashda raqamli texnologiyalardan foydalanishning o'rni (oliy ta'lim misolida) 385 Axrorov Voris Yunusovich, Boltayeva Jaxona Ulug'bek qizi	385	
Umumta'lim maktablarida 7-sinf biologiya fanini o'qitishda virtual laboratoriyalardan foydalanishning ta'lim samaradorligiga ta'siri 389 Turakulova Mehriniso Nuriddinovna, Ruziqulova Nilufar Abdumajidovna, Allanzarova Natalya Aleuatdinovna	389	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarni maktabga tayyorlashning mavjud holati va rivojlantirish strategiyalari ... 393 Mamadaliyeva Mumtozbegim	393	
6–7 yoshli bolalarning bilim olishga faol qiziqishini rivojlantirish metodikasi 396 Artikova Muhayyo Botiraliyevna, Abduxolisova Gulsanam O'ktambek qizi	396	
The Main Peculiarities of Abbreviations in Modern English..... 399 Absalomova Aziza Baxodir qizi	399	
Autizmli bolalarni maktab ta'limiga tayyorlashda bir qator terapiya va metodlardan foydalanish 404 Yoqubova Hurriyat Burxonovna	404	
Boshlang'ich ta'limda o'yinlar, virtual reallik va geymifikatsiya orqali o'quvchilarning motivatsiyasini oshirish..... 407 Xaitova Nazokat	407	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining ijodiy ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishda tabiiy materiallardan foydalanishning pedagogik usullari..... 411 Rustamova Manzura Mirkamalovna, Qo'ziyeva Umriniso Muzaffar qizi	411	
Bo'lajak muhandislarning loyihalash ko'nikmalarini klaster muhitida rivojlantirish modellari..... 415 Eshonqulova Shafoat Ergashevna, Sherzod Eshonqulov	415	
Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotini rivojlantirish strategiyalarini ishlab chiqish 420 Ermatova Mamlakat Qadirkulovna	420	
9-sinf o'quvchilarini kasbga yo'naltirishda iqtisodiy ko'nikmalarni shakllantirish pedagogik muammo sifatida..... 423 Eliboyeva Lola Sulaymonovna	423	

Texnologiya asosidagi ingliz tili o'qitish va o'quvchi mustaqilligi: farmatsevtika talabalari misolida	427
Ikramova Shohsanam Ravshanboy qizi	
Maqollar asosida ingliz tili o'qitishning lingvodidaktik asoslari (Afg'oniston dariy tilli maktablar misolida) ..	430
Samadi Nooria	
Loyihaga asoslangan ta'lim texnologiyasi orqali talabalarda ijtimoiy mas'uliyat kompetensiyasini rivojlantirish tadqiqi	434
Jo'rayeva Zebiniso Yo'ldoshevna	
Boshlang'ich sinfda tabiiy fanlarni o'qitish samaradorligini oshirishda innovatsion va zamonaviy pedagogik texnologiyalardan foydalanish	440
Yulchiyeva Zulfia Baxodir qizi	
Shaxsning individual intellektual rivojlanishi pedagogik muammo sifatida	444
Oltiboyeva Kamola Sharofjon qizi	
Boshlang'ich ta'limda o'yin texnologiyalaridan foydalanish orqali o'quvchilar qiziqishini aniqlash yo'llari ...	448
Qalandarova Yulduz G'ayrat qizi	
Проблемы физического воспитания студентов и пути их решения.....	454
Ходжанов Азиз Рахимович	
Maktabgacha katta yoshdagi bolalarda axloqiy qadriyatlarni shakllantirishda milliy ertaklardan foydalanish texnologiyasi.....	458
Kayumova Nargiza Mirziyatovna	
Jamiyatda sog'lom turmush tarzini tashkil qilishda jismoniy tarbiya va sport mutaxassislarining o'rni.....	461
Dehqonova Mahmuda Ortiqovna	
Yadro itqitish sport turida kuch tayyorgarligining biomexanik va funksional ahamiyati.....	466
Djabbarov Axror Islomovich	
Kompetensiyaviy yondashuv asosida bo'lajak boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilarining didaktik tayyorgarligini takomillashtirish.....	469
Axmedova Laylo Baxtiyor qizi	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida tayanch kompetensiyalarni rivojlantirishda shaxsga yo'naltirilgan strategiyalar.....	475
Urazimbetova Aygul Aralbayevna	
Eshitishda nuqsoni bo'lgan bolalar nutqini rivojlantirishda kompyuter texnologiyalarining pedagogik imkoniyatlari	482
Kamolova Yulduzxon Ma'murjon qizi	
Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlarida ma'naviy-ma'rifiy ishlarni tashkil etishda ota-onalar bilan hamkorlikni amalga oshirish texnologiyasi.....	488
Kasimova Dilrabo Baxadirovna, Jo'rabayeva Nozima Bekmurod qizi	
Psixologik zo'ravonlik oqibatlarini bartaraf etishda psixokorreksion mexanizmlar.....	491
Tursunpo'latova Zaxro Zafar qizi	
Shifokorlar professional karerasi resurslari va ularning obyektiv ko'rsatkichlari o'rtasidagi bog'liqlikni o'rganish natijalari.....	496
Arziqulov O'tkirbek Maxammatovich	
Bolalarda maktabgacha ta'lim yoshidagi kommunikativ qobiliyatlarni rivojlantirishda ijodiy o'yinlarning o'rni	501
Berdiyeva Umida G'oyibberdiyevna	
Maktabgacha katta yoshdagi bolalarning neyropedagogik yondashuvlar asosida kognitiv rivojlantirishning mohiyati.....	505
Aliyeva Odila Madamin qizi	
Emotional Intelligence and Perceptive Ability: Keys to Pedagogical Success	508
Abdurakhimov Shokhasim Abdurakhmonovich	
Bo'lajak logopedlarni og'ir nutq nuqsonli bolalar bilan ishlashga tayyorlashning nazariy asoslari	511
Achilova Sevara Djasirkulovna	
Abdulla Avloniy pedagogik g'oyalarini zamonaviy boshlang'ich ta'lim bilan integratsiyalash	515
Daliyeva Eliza Zokir qizi	

MUNDARIJA СОДЕРЖАНИЕ CONTENTS	Talabalarda ma'naviy-axloqiy sifatlarni rivojlantirishda Mahmud Qoshg'ariy merosidan foydalanish..... 519 Eliboyeva Lola Sulaymonovna, Ravshanova Sarvinoz O'ktamjon qizi
	Derivation and Nominalization in Medical Terminology: A Comparative Model of Term and Process Name Formation in English and Uzbek 523 Gulnigor Yazdonkulova
	Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarning nutq buzilishlarida pedagogik-psixologik korreksiya usullari hamda mexanizmlari..... 526 Jo'rayeva Muattar Abdumajit qizi
	Ta'lim sifatini boshqarishga tizimli yondashish hamda pedagogikada PDCA modelining ahamiyati 530 Jumanazarova Gulloila Yoqubjanovna, Xolmatova Maftuna Turdimat qizi
	Sun'iy intellekt asosidagi ta'lim vositalarining kimyo ta'limidagi o'rni..... 535 Jumaniyazova Mahliyo Qahramonovna
	Inklyuziv maktab sharoitida kichik maktab yoshidagi bolalarda ijtimoiy-perseptiv tajribani shakllantirish ... 539 Karimova Zulfiya Abduraxmanovna
	Sirdaryo viloyati toponimlarining shakllanish jarayonlari 543 Kenjayeva Iroda Alisherovna
	Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarni maktab ta'limiga tayyorlashda art texnologiyalardan foydalanishning nazariy-metodologik asoslari 546 Mamatova Husnora Eshquvatovna
	O'quvchi yoshlarning innovatsion fikrlashini rivojlantirish va uni amaliy faoliyat bilan integratsiyalash 550 Mehmonova Nilufar Shuhratovna
	Integrating Social-Emotional Learning in EFL Classrooms: Enhancing Language Proficiency and Emotional Intelligence 553 Meylinorova Feruza Bakhtiyor kizi
	Nodavlat ta'lim tashkilotlari pedagog-tarbiyachilarining malakasini oshirish mexanizmini takomillashtirish 559 Muminova Nargiza Sabitdjanovna
	TEACCH konsepsiyasi – autizm va kommunikativ buzilishlari bo'lgan bolalarni davolash va o'qitish dasturi 562 Murodova Sarvigul Raxim qizi
	Aksiologik yondashuvlar asosida bo'lajak pedagoglarda altruizm ko'nikmalarini shakllantirishning funksional modeli 566 Norboyeva Moxigul Shavkat qizi
	Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlarida o'yin texnologiyalari asosida bolalarning shaxsiy va ijtimoiy kompetensiyalarini takomillashtirish 569 Norqulova Ma'mura Husniddin qizi
	Umumiy o'rta ta'lim maktablarining 6-sinfida o'qitiladigan "Tabiiy fanlar"dan mashg'ulotlarni tashkil etish metodikasi..... 574 Qo'qonboyeva Shaxlo Rafikjonovna
	The Intersection of Science and Pedagogy: The Teacher's Role in Professional Evolution 580 Rahimberdiyev Rustam Abdunasirovich, Shukurova Madina
	Maktabgacha katta guruhlarida STEAM texnologiyasi bilan tanishtirishning pedagogik-psixologik xususiyatlari 583 Rakhimova Laylo Hamidjon qizi
	Hamshiralik ishida raqamli texnologiyalardan foydalanishning samaradorligi..... 586 Rasulova Gulmira, Amonova Dildora, Abdurahmonov Aziz, Hakimova X. X.
	Kurashchilarda muvozanat (balance) va ko'tarib uloqtirish texnikasi o'rtasidagi bog'liqlik 590 Shermatov Gulom Qaxxorovich
	O'qituvchi shaxsining o'zini o'zi rivojlantirishida akmeologik pozitsiyaning o'rni..... 594 Xaitov Abdulkosim Abdulkalim o'g'li
	Lego-qurilish, konstruksiyalash, robototexnika – STEAM ta'lim moduli sifatida 596 Xamroyeva Sitara Samadovna

Raqamli jamiyatda o'smir yoshdagi o'quvchilarning huquqiy axborot olish madaniyatini rivojlantirish mexanizmlari	599
<i>Xayrullayev Axror Aktam o'g'li</i>	
Maktabgacha ta'limda axborot kommunikatsiya texnologiyalari yordamida ta'limiy o'yinlarni loyihalash va joriy etish	602
<i>Xikmatova Moxinur Amir qizi</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinflarda tabiiy fanlar orqali kognitiv qobiliyatlarni rivojlantirish zamonaviy yechimlarini ishlab chiqish usullari	605
<i>Xolmo'minova Mohichehra Bahrom qizi</i>	
O'quvchilarning biologiyaga qiziqishini oshirishda innovatsion ta'lim metodlari	609
<i>Xudayberganova Madina Saotboy qizi, Abdiqodirov Murodho'ja Alisher o'g'li, Nishanbayeva Arayim User qizi</i>	
Oliy ta'lim muassasalarida shug'ullanuvchi voleybolchi qizlarning musobaqa oldi jismoniy va psixologik tayyorgarligini takomillashtirish metodikasi	612
<i>Xudoynazarova Sayyora Ravshanovna</i>	
Maktabgacha ta'limda milliy qadriyatlar asosida bolalarni axloqiy tarbiyalash texnologiyalari	618
<i>Yo'ldoshboyeva Gulmira Xushnudovna</i>	
Umumta'lim maktab seksiyasi uzunlikka sakrovchilarining jismoniy rivojlanganlik darajasi	621
<i>Zokir Akramov O'tkir o'g'li</i>	
Perseptiv qobiliyat: o'qituvchining o'quvchini tushunish sa'nati	625
<i>Zokirov Mirzaraxim Abdaliyevich</i>	
Ожидания и потребности родителей как основа продвижения услуг дошкольного образовательного учреждения в Республике Узбекистан	628
<i>Ким Ирина Николаевна, Аббосхонова Зухра Баходир кизи</i>	
Экспериментальная деятельность – метод развития здоровьесберегающей компетентности у детей старшего дошкольного возраста	631
<i>Ким Ирина Николаевна, Алиходжаева Райхон Шавкат кизи</i>	
Подготовка детей-билингвов к школьному обучению: интеграция цифровых и традиционных педагогических методов	634
<i>Ким Ирина Николаевна, Умарова Шоиста Рустамовна</i>	

DERIVATION AND NOMINALIZATION IN MEDICAL TERMINOLOGY: A COMPARATIVE MODEL OF TERM AND PROCESS NAME FORMATION IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK

Gulnigir Yazdonkulova

Teacher in Samarkand state institute of foreign languages

Abstract: Derivation and nominalization play a central role in the formation of medical terminology, enabling the systematic naming of processes, conditions, and clinical procedures. The present study aims to develop a comparative model of derivational and nominalization mechanisms in English and Uzbek medical terminology. Drawing on data from international medical classifications, specialized dictionaries, and academic corpora, the study analyzes structural patterns, functional differences, and semantic transparency in both languages. The findings demonstrate that English exhibits a highly productive nominalization system based on Greek–Latin affixes, whereas Uzbek relies on a hybrid model combining borrowed nominal forms with native verbal–nominal constructions. The study highlights typological factors shaping term formation and proposes principles for terminological standardization in Uzbek medical discourse.

Key words: derivation, nominalization, medical terminology, word formation, English, Uzbek.

Annotatsiya: Derivatsiya va nominalizatsiya tibbiy terminologiya shakllanishida muhim o‘rin tutib, jarayonlar, holatlar hamda klinik muolajalarni tizimli tarzda nomlash imkonini beradi. Mazkur tadqiqot ingliz va o‘zbek tillarida tibbiy terminologiyada derivatsiya va nominalizatsiya mexanizmlarining qiyosiy modelini ishlab chiqishga qaratilgan. Tadqiqot xalqaro tibbiy tasniflar, maxsus lug‘atlar va akademik korpuslar ma‘lumotlariga asoslanib, har ikki tilda strukturaviy model-lar, funksional farqlar hamda semantik shaffoflikni tahlil qiladi. Natijalar ingliz tilida yunon–lotin affikslari asosida shakl-langan yuqori darajada produktiv nominalizatsiya tizimi mavjudligini, o‘zbek tilida esa o‘zlashgan nominal shakllar bilan bir qatorda mahalliy fe‘l–ot konstruksiyalarini o‘z ichiga olgan gibrid model ustunligini ko‘rsatadi. Tadqiqot terminlar yasa-lishiga ta‘sir etuvchi tipologik omillarni yoritib, o‘zbek tibbiy diskursida terminologiyani standartlashtirish tamoyillarini taklif etadi.

Kalit so‘zlar: derivatsiya, nominalizatsiya, tibbiy terminologiya, so‘z yasalishi, ingliz tili, o‘zbek tili.

Аннотация: Деривация и номинализация играют ключевую роль в формировании медицинской терминологии, обеспечивая системное наименование процессов, состояний и клинических процедур. Целью настоящего исследования является разработка сравнительной модели механизмов деривации и номинализации в медицинской терминологии английского и узбекского языков. На основе данных международных медицинских классификаций, специализированных словарей и академических корпусов в работе анализируются структурные модели, функциональные различия и семантическая прозрачность в обоих языках. Полученные результаты свидетельствуют о том, что в английском языке функционирует высокопродуктивная система номинализации, основанная на греко-латинских аффиксах, тогда как в узбекском языке преобладает гибридная модель, сочетающая заимствованные номинальные формы с собственными глагольно-именными конструкциями. В исследовании выявляются типологические факторы, определяющие процессы словообразования, и предлагаются принципы стандартизации терминологии в узбекском медицинском дискурсе.

Ключевые слова: деривация, номинализация, медицинская терминология, словообразование, английский язык, узбекский язык.

INTRODUCTION

Medical terminology represents one of the most structurally regulated domains of scientific language, characterized by precision, consistency, and conceptual clarity. Among the various word-formation mechanisms employed in this domain, derivation and nominalization are particularly significant, as they enable the transformation of actions, processes, and states into stable terminological units. Such transformations are essential

for encoding complex medical knowledge in a compact and internationally intelligible form. In English, medical nominalization is largely realized through Greek–Latin derivational affixes, allowing verbs and adjectives to be converted into nouns denoting diseases, procedures, and physiological processes. In Uzbek, however, the formation of medical process names reflects the typological features of a Turkic agglutinative language, resulting in a combination of borrowed nominal forms and native analytical constructions. This study seeks to compare these mechanisms and to propose a unified model for understanding derivation and nominalization in English and Uzbek medical terminology.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Previous linguistic research has consistently emphasized the central role of derivation and nominalization in scientific and medical discourse. Scholars note that nominalization facilitates abstraction and objectification, which are essential for scientific reasoning and classification. In medical terminology, Greek–Latin derivational morphology provides a highly productive system for naming pathological conditions, diagnostic procedures, and therapeutic interventions. Studies on English medical discourse demonstrate that nominalized forms dominate academic and clinical texts, contributing to terminological density and informational compression. In contrast, research on Turkic languages indicates a preference for verbal or descriptive constructions, particularly in patient-oriented communication. Although several studies describe the formation of medical terms in individual languages, comparative analyses focusing specifically on derivation and nominalization across typologically distinct languages remain limited. Moreover, corpus-based investigations of Uzbek medical terminology are still underrepresented, underscoring the need for systematic contrastive research.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study adopts a comparative descriptive-analytical approach, integrating methods from contrastive linguistics and terminology studies. The research material consists of a corpus of approximately 600 medical terms and process names extracted from international classifications (ICD-11, MeSH), English and bilingual medical dictionaries, and contemporary academic medical texts. The selected terms include nominalized forms derived from verbs and adjectives, as well as compound constructions denoting medical processes. Morphological analysis was employed to identify derivational patterns and nominalization strategies in each language. Semantic analysis was conducted to assess meaning transparency and conceptual stability. A contrastive framework was applied to compare productivity, structural types, and functional usage in English and Uzbek. Quantitative methods were used to determine the frequency of nominalized forms and their distribution across medical subdomains.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The analysis revealed significant differences in the use of derivation and nominalization in English and Uzbek medical terminology. In English, nominalization is a highly productive and dominant mechanism, primarily realized through Greek–Latin suffixes such as *-tion*, *-sis*, *-ment*, *-ity*, and *-osis*. These suffixes systematically convert verbal and adjectival bases into nouns denoting medical processes (diagnose → diagnosis, operate → operation, inflate → inflation), thereby ensuring semantic precision and terminological consistency. In Uzbek, nominalization occurs through two principal strategies. The first involves the direct borrowing of nominalized forms (diagnosis → *tashxis*, operation → *operatsiya*), often mediated by Russian. The second strategy relies on native verbal–nominal constructions, employing affixes and auxiliary elements to express processes (*tekshirish*, *davolash jarayoni*, *operatsiya qilish*). While borrowed nominal forms are prevalent in professional medical discourse, native constructions occur more frequently in explanatory and educational contexts. Quantitative analysis indicates that nominalized terms constitute approximately 65% of process-related terminology in English medical texts, compared to 38% in Uzbek. The remaining Uzbek terms are expressed through analytic constructions, reflecting a lower degree of morphological compression.

The findings demonstrate that derivation and nominalization function differently in English and Uzbek due to typological and functional factors. English exhibits a morphologically dense system in which nominalization serves as the primary means of conceptualizing medical processes. This system aligns with the international nature of medical discourse and supports efficient knowledge transmission among professionals. Uzbek, by contrast, employs a hybrid model that balances international terminological norms with native linguistic resources. While borrowed nominal forms ensure alignment with global medical standards, native verbal–nominal constructions enhance semantic transparency and communicative accessibility. This dual system, however, may result in inconsistency and variation in terminology usage across different communicative contexts. From a terminological perspective, the results suggest that excessive reliance on borrowed nominal-

izations without systematic regulation may hinder the development of a coherent national medical terminology. At the same time, complete replacement with descriptive constructions may reduce international compatibility. Therefore, a balanced approach that integrates standardized nominal forms with clearly defined functional domains is recommended.

CONCLUSION

This study presents a comparative model of derivation and nominalization in English and Uzbek medical terminology, highlighting structural, semantic, and functional differences between the two languages. English relies on a highly productive system of affix-based nominalization, whereas Uzbek adopts a hybrid strategy that combines borrowed nominal forms with native analytic constructions. The findings contribute to comparative linguistics, terminology studies, and medical translation by offering insights into the standardization and optimization of medical process naming in Uzbek. Future research may expand this model through the use of larger corpora and experimental studies on term comprehension.

References:

1. Wulff, H. R. (2004). The language of medicine. *Journal of the Royal Society of Medicine*, 97(4), 187–188. <https://doi.org/10.1177/014107680409700406>
2. Temmerman, R. (2011). *Terminology and translation*. Amsterdam: John Benjamins Publishing Company. <https://doi.org/10.1075/btl.94>
3. Baker, M. (2018). *In other words: A coursebook on translation* (3rd ed.). London: Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315619187>
4. Sager, J. C. (1990). *A practical course in terminology processing*. Amsterdam: John Benjamins.

-
- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

MAKTABGACHA VA MAKTAB TA'LIMI

Mas'ul muharrir: Ramzidin Ashurov

Ingliz tili muharriri: Murod Xoliyorov

Musahhih: Alibek Zokirov

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Iskandar Islomov

2026. №2(1)

© Materiallar ko'chirib bosilganda "Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi" jurnali manba sifatida ko'rsatilishi shart. Jurnalda bosilgan material va reklamalardagi dalillarning aniqligiga mualliflar ma'sul. Tahririyat fikri har vaqt ham mualliflar fikriga mos kelmasligi mumkin. Tahririyatga yuborilgan materiallar qaytarilmaydi.

"Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi" jurnali 26.09.2023-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №C-5669363 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.
Litsenziya raqami: № 136361.

Manzirimiz: Toshkent shahar, Yunusobod tumani
19-mavze, 17-uy.